

An Assessment of Librarians' Awareness of Cloud Computing Technologies for Enhanced Service Delivery in University Libraries in North-East Nigeria

Peter Yohanna Mshelia¹; Ifraimu Lawan Istifanus²; Philip Gana Malgwi³; Samaila Inuwa⁴

^{1,2,4}University of Maiduguri, Borno State; ³Federal University of Technology Otuoke

¹petermshelia@unimaid.edu.ng;

²ifraimuisty@unimaid.edu.ng;

³philmalgwi@gmail.com

⁴inuwasamaila24@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study examined the level of awareness of Cloud Computing Technologies (CCT) among librarians in university libraries in North-East Nigeria and compared differences across Federal, State, and Private institutions. An evaluative survey research design was adopted, and the population comprised 369 professional and para-professional librarians from six university libraries. A structured questionnaire was administered to all respondents, with 273 valid copies retrieved for analysis. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, and mean), while One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to test for differences in awareness across institutional types at a 0.05 level of significance. A post-hoc analysis using Hochberg's GT2 test was conducted to assess specific group differences. The findings revealed moderate awareness of CCT among librarians, with an overall mean score of 2.82 on a five-point scale. Social networking applications and online databases showed high awareness, whereas institutional repositories, discovery tools, and information collection services showed relatively low awareness. The ANOVA results indicated a statistically significant difference in librarians' awareness across institutional types ($p < 0.05$). Post-hoc analysis showed no significant difference between Federal and State university libraries; however, Private university libraries exhibited significantly higher awareness levels than their Federal and State counterparts. The study concludes that although librarians in the region demonstrate moderate awareness of cloud computing technologies, notable disparities exist across institutional ownership. The study recommends sustained professional development programmes, institutional ICT investment, and inter-library collaboration to enhance librarians' awareness and readiness for effective deployment of cloud-based library services.

Keywords: Cloud Computing Technologies, Librarians, University Libraries, Awareness, North East, Nigeria

Introduction

Libraries, as custodians and managers of information, must continuously adapt to prevailing technological trends to remain relevant in efficient service delivery. While physical collections have historically defined library spaces, rapid digital transformation within the information environment has necessitated a shift toward technology-enabled services. Contemporary academic libraries increasingly extend their presence beyond physical walls, offering resources and services that are accessible globally and on demand through

digital platforms. This trend reflects broader advances in information and communication technologies (ICT), which empower libraries to process, disseminate, and manage information irrespective of time or physical location (Ejedafiru & Ogbogbaidi, 2024; Anike & Otubelu, 2025).

Before the widespread adoption of advanced ICT infrastructures, many library operations, including circulation, cataloguing, reference services, and bibliographic control, were largely manual and isolated. The emergence of digital library systems and automation technologies has significantly improved the efficiency and coordination of these services. More recently, cloud computing technologies have further transformed library operations by providing scalable, network-based solutions that support integrated service delivery across distributed environments. Unlike traditional Integrated Library Systems (ILS), cloud-based Library Service Platforms (LSPs) leverage web-hosted architectures to deliver cost-effective, scalable, and interoperable services, including seamless integration with institutional learning management systems and other academic technologies (Kouis & Agiorgitis, 2020).

Cloud computing represents a dynamic technological paradigm that enables on-demand access to computing resources and applications through internet connectivity without requiring local installation or infrastructure management (Kumar, 2021). Its major service models are Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS), which allow organisations to optimise operational efficiency, enhance collaboration, and reduce infrastructure costs. Among these models, Software as a Service has become particularly relevant for libraries because it supports the deployment of cloud-hosted applications with minimal technical expertise and reduced maintenance requirements (Onwubiko et al., 2021).

As libraries increasingly transition from desktop-based systems to cloud-enabled environments, the need for librarians to develop relevant digital competencies becomes more critical. Switching services to the cloud environments or running services alongside the traditional library routine will afford the libraries the opportunities to revolutionise service delivery in present-day libraries (Irenea et al., 2018). Cloud computing technologies can enhance library services by supporting digital repositories, online databases, collaborative platforms, and remote access to scholarly resources. However, effective utilisation of these technologies depends largely on librarians' knowledge, technical skills, and readiness to integrate them into professional practice (Akinyoola, 2023).

Awareness is a fundamental prerequisite for successful technology adoption. It encompasses familiarity, understanding, and motivation, which collectively influence whether individuals accept and utilise new technologies effectively. When awareness is inadequate, organisations may invest in technologies that remain underutilised, thereby limiting their potential benefits. In most cases, libraries in Nigerian universities utilise only the technologies and facilities they are aware of and that are readily available to them (Aiyebilehin et al., 2020). This implies a direct correlation between awareness and system penetration; increased awareness fosters adoption, while a lack thereof hinders utilisation, undermining the system's intended purpose. Consequently, librarians' awareness of cloud computing technologies constitutes a crucial step toward successful adoption and integration into library services (Solomon & Bakare, 2022; Idahosa & Eireyi-Edewede, 2023; Dumbiri et al., 2024).

Empirical studies conducted in Nigerian academic library contexts reveal varying levels of awareness and utilisation of cloud computing technologies. For instance, Dumbiri et al. (2024) found that librarians in

colleges of education commonly use cloud-based tools such as Google Drive and Gmail for information sharing and collaboration, indicating growing familiarity with cloud applications. Similarly, Ejedafiru and Ogbogbaidi (2024) reported positive awareness and perceptions of cloud technologies among librarians in state-owned universities, although infrastructural and technical challenges still limit optimal utilisation.

Conversely, other studies suggest that awareness and professional application of cloud computing remain uneven across institutions, particularly where training opportunities and technological infrastructure are limited. These findings highlight the need for targeted capacity-building initiatives, professional development programmes, and institutional support strategies to strengthen librarians' competencies and readiness for cloud technology adoption (Idahosa & Eireyi-Edewede, 2023; Akinyoola, 2023).

Although Nigerian academic libraries have made notable progress in integrating digital technologies into their services, persistent challenges, including limited infrastructure, inadequate technical expertise, and uneven awareness levels, continue to constrain the full realisation of cloud-based library systems. Understanding librarians' awareness levels and institutional disparities is, therefore, essential for improving technology adoption and enhancing the effectiveness of service delivery. It is against this backdrop that this study investigates librarians' awareness of cloud computing technologies in university libraries in North-East Nigeria.

Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the librarians' level of awareness of CCT in University libraries in North-East, Nigeria;
2. Compare the difference between librarians' level of awareness of CCT among Federal, State and Private University libraries in North-East Nigeria;

Hypothesis

The hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between Librarians' level of Awareness of CCT Adoption among federal, state, and private university libraries in North-East, Nigeria.

Methodology

The survey research design was used for this study. The population for the study was three hundred and sixty-nine (369) librarians of the six (6) University libraries studied. The six (6) libraries were Ramat Library, University of Maiduguri, University Library, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Robert Pastor Library, American University of Nigeria, Yola, Kwararafa University Library, Wukari, Goodluck Ebele Jonathan Library, Yobe State University, Damaturu and Abdulrahman Gaji Library, Adamawa State University, Mubi, Adamawa State. The entire population was used for the study. This is because the population of 369 librarians is manageable. This is in line with Gall and Borg (2007), who stress that the entire population should be studied when the entire population is manageable. The research instrument for this study was a self-designed questionnaire. Cronbach's Alpha reliability analysis was run to assess the instrument's internal consistency, yielding a value of 0.896, indicating very strong reliability.

Descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentage scores, and means were used to analyse the data to answer the research question; the results were presented in tables. Inferential statistics using One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to test the formulated hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance to determine whether there was a significant difference among Federal, State, and Private university libraries in terms of awareness of CCT. To determine group differences and the level of significance, post-hoc statistics with Hochberg’s GT2 were used to test multiple comparisons of the libraries by type (proprietorship) and to identify significant differences among the libraries. The choice of Hochberg’s GT2 test was considered ideal over other methods given the unequal sample sizes between groups (Field, 2009, p. 545). The analysis was carried out using SPSS version 23.

Results and Discussion

Three hundred and sixty-nine (369) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to respondents across all six (6) surveyed university libraries in North-East Nigeria. Of the 369 copies distributed, 273 were filled out, returned, and found usable. This gives a response rate of 74%.

Table 4.1.1 presents the response rate for the questionnaires distributed and returned in the surveyed university libraries.

Demographic Information

Table 4.1. 1: The Respondents’ Library, Gender, Age group and Work Experience.

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Respondent's Library		
Abdulrahman Gaji Library, Adamawa State University, Mubi	20	7.3
ATBU Library, Bauchi	78	28.6
Kwararafa University Library, Wukari	7	2.6
Ramat Library, University of Maiduguri	124	45.4
Robert Pastor Library, American University of Nigeria (AUN)	11	4.0
Goodluck Ebele Jonathan Library, Yobe State University	33	12.1
Total	273	100

Source: Researchers’ survey 2025

Table 4.1.1 presents the demographic information of the respondents by library. Accordingly, Ramat Library, University of Maiduguri, had the highest number of respondents, 124 (45.4%), followed at a distance by the Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Library, Bauchi, with 78 respondents, representing 28.6% of the count. Goodluck Ebele Jonathan Library, Yobe State University 33(12.1%), Abdulrahman Gaji Library, Adamawa State University 20(7.3%), Robert Pastor Library, American University of Nigeria (AUN) 11(4.0%) and Kwararafa University Library, Wukari, 7(2.6%) in that order. The table shows that the majority, 186 (68.1%) of the respondents, are male, and 87 (31.9%) are female.

The age group scores in Table 4.1.1 revealed that majority of the respondents were between the age of 41 to 50 with a score of 84(30.8%), followed by age group between 31 to 40 with a score of 82(30.0%), age group between 20 to 30 with score of 78(28.6%) and the age group of 50 and above were the least with a score of 29(10.6%). This implies 60.8% of the respondents' age range from 31 to 50 were in the active

age. The 28.6% of the age range 20 to 30 years signifies hope for the future of the library's growth with youths.

Information regarding respondents' working experience in Table 4.4.1 revealed that those who had 4 to 10 years of working experience are the majority 85(31.1%) followed by those with more than 10 years of working experience 78(28.6%), 1 to 3 years of working experience 69(25.3%) and respondents with less than 1-year work experience being the least which accounted for 41(15%) of the respondents.

Research Question 2: What is the level of Awareness of the following CCT in your Library?

Table 4.1. 2: Level of Awareness CCT in Libraries

	N	Not Aware	Slightly Aware	Somewhat Aware	Aware	Extremely Aware	Mean	Decision
1 Institutional repository (e.g., Dspace, E-prints, Fedora, Digital Commons)		103 (37.7%)	47 (17.2%)	55 (20.1%)	43 (15.8%)	25 (9.2%)	2.40	Reject
2 Social networking (e.g., Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, WhatsApp)	273	6 (2.2%)	31 (11.4%)	59 (21.6%)	96 (35.2%)	81 (29.7%)	3.79	Accept
3 Databases (e.g., Science Direct, EBSCOhost, Hinari, Agora, Proquest)		16 (5.9%)	35 (12.3%)	66 (24.2%)	104 (38.1%)	52 (19%)	3.52	Accept
4 WorldCat		70 (25.6%)	58 (21.2%)	51 (18.7%)	76 (27.8%)	18 (6.6%)	2.69	Accept
5 Hosting Library website		38 (13.9%)	57 (20.9%)	62 (22.7%)	77 (28.2%)	39 (14.3%)	3.08	Accept
6 Google Apps (Google Drive, Google Doc)		61 (22.3%)	61 (22.3%)	69 (25.3%)	55 (20.1%)	27 (9.9%)	2.73	Accept

7	Cloud File Sharing Services (e.g., Google Drive, Microsoft OneDrive, Dropbox)	53 (19.4%)	70 (25.6%)	63 (23.1%)	55 (20.1%)	32 (11.7%)	2.79	Accept
8	Webinar Services (EasyWebinar, GoTo Webinar, Webex, Google Meet)	61 (22.3%)	92 (33.7%)	52 (19%)	40 (14.7%)	28 (10.3%)	2.57	Accept
9	Virtual References services (LibChat, QuestionPoint, Ask a Librarian)	47 (17.2%)	88 (32.2%)	52 (19%)	65 (23.8%)	21 (7.7%)	2.73	Accept
10	Information Collection Services (e.g., Google Form, Survey Monkey, Survey Ocean, Survey Planet)	104 (38.1%)	54 (19.8%)	26 (9.5%)	60 (22.0%)	29 (10.6%)	2.47	Reject
11	Discovery tools (e.g., ExLibris Primo, Summon, OCLC WorldCat Discovery Services, BiblioCore, etc.)	112 (41%)	56 (20.5%)	44 (16.1%)	42 (15.4%)	19 (7.0%)	2.27	Reject
	Average frequencies, percentages and mean.	61 (22.33%)	59 (21.61%)	55 (20.15%)	65 (23.81%)	33 (12.09%)	2.82	Accept

The respondent's level of awareness of the following CCT was measured with eleven (11) items in Table 4.1.3. The information indicates that 103(37.7%) respondents were not aware, 47(17.2%) were slightly aware, 55(20.1%) were somewhat aware, 43(15.8%) were aware, while 25(9.2%) were extremely aware of Institutional repositories such as Dspace, E-prints, Fedora, and Digital Commons. The awareness of institutional repositories, with a mean of 2.40, indicated that the level of awareness is below average. Social networking applications like Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, and WhatsApp received 6(2.2%) not aware, 31(11.4%) slightly aware, 59(21.6%) somewhat aware, 96(35.2%) aware and 81(29.7%) extremely aware. The awareness for social networking applications with a mean=3.79 indicated that the level of awareness is high among the respondents. The respondent's awareness of databases indicates that 16(5.9%) were not aware, 35(12.3%) were slightly aware, 66(24.2%) were somewhat aware, 104(38.1%) aware and 52(19%) were extremely aware. The awareness of Databases with a mean=3.52 indicated that the level of awareness among the respondents is high. The respondent's awareness of WorldCat indicates that 70(25.6%) were not aware, 58(21.2%) were slightly aware, 51(18.7%) were somewhat aware, 76(27.8%) and 18(6.6%) were aware and extremely aware respectively. The level awareness of WorldCat among the respondents with a mean=2.69 indicated slightly above average. Awareness of hosting Library website, the response showed that 38(13.9%) were not aware of it, 57(20.9%) were slightly aware, 62(22.7%) were somewhat aware 77(28.2%) were aware while 39(14.3%) were extremely aware of it. The awareness of Hosting Library website among the respondents with a mean=3.08 indicated to be above average. A total of 61(22.3%) respondents were not aware of Google Apps (Google Drive, Google Doc), 61(22.3%) were slightly aware 69(25.3%) were somewhat aware, 55(20.1%) were aware while 27(9.9%) were extremely aware of it. The awareness of Google Apps among the respondents with a mean=2.73 indicated that the level is slightly above average. Awareness of Cloud File Sharing Services such as google drive, Microsoft OneDrive and Dropbox scored 53(19.4%), 70(25.6%), 63(23.1%), 55(20.1%), and 32(11.7%) for not aware, slightly aware, somewhat aware, aware and extremely aware respectively. Awareness of Cloud file Sharing Services among the respondent with a mean=2.79 indicated that the level of awareness is above average. Other cloud computing resources such as Webinar Services, Virtual References services, and Information Collection Services received various types of responses as can be seen in the table. Response on Discovery tools like ExLibris Primo, Summon, OCLC etc., indicate that 112(41%) were not aware 56(20.5%) were slightly aware, 44(16.1%) and 42 (15.4%) were aware and extremely aware respectively; with a mean=2.27 indicated that the level of awareness among the respondents is below average. In summary, awareness of the following CCT in libraries is slightly above average with an average mean score of 2.82 on a scale of 5 points. The average frequency score indicates that 61(22.33%) respondents were not aware, 59(21.61%) were slightly aware, 55(20.15%) are somewhat aware, 65(23.81%) were aware while 33(12.09%) were extremely aware of the above-listed CCT in libraries under study. The mean score of 2.82 on a scale of 5 indicated that the level of awareness of CCT among the librarians of the university libraries under study can be accepted, thus it can be construed that the librarians were aware of CCT since the mean is slightly above the minimum of 2.5, thus it is considered to be at moderate level.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between Librarians' level of awareness of CCT adoption among Federal, State and Private University Libraries in NE, Nigeria.

Table 4.1. 3: One Way ANOVA of Librarians' level of awareness in CCT adoption among Federal, State and Private University libraries

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	20.832	2	10.416	13.913	.000
Within Groups	202.140	270	.749		
Total	222.972	272			

Table 4.1.8 reveals the result of one-way ANOVA ($F(2,270) = 13.913, p = .000$), F-test greater than critical f-value ($13.913 > 1.96$) and p value less than the alpha level ($.000 < 0.05$). This indicates that there are differences in librarians' levels of awareness of CCT adoption across Federal, State, and Private University libraries in NE, Nigeria. A further test of the group differences and the level of significance, post-hoc statistics with Hochberg's GT2, was required to reveal multiple comparisons of the libraries by type and significant differences among the libraries (Table 4.1.9 and 4.1.9.1).

Table 4.1. 4: Post-Hoc Hochberg's GT2 Multiple Comparison of the Libraries by type on the difference between Librarians' levels of awareness in CCT Adoption

(I) Libraries according to type	(J) Libraries according to type	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Federal University Library	State University Library	-.08559	.13354	.798
	Private University Library	-1.12266*	.21284	.000
State University Library	Federal University Library	.08559	.13354	.798
	Private University Library	-1.03707*	.23605	.000
Private University Library	Federal University Library	1.12266*	.21284	.000
	State University Library	1.03707*	.23605	.000

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 4.1.9. 1: Multiple Comparisons

Test	p-value (sig.)	Significant?
Federal University Library vs State University Library	.798	No
Federal University Library vs Private University Library	.000	Yes
State University Library vs Private University Library	.000	Yes

Multiple comparisons of the libraries by type regarding Librarians' levels of awareness of CCT adoption in Table 4.1.9 revealed a non-significant difference in librarians' awareness level of CCT and adoption between Federal and State University Library at $p = .798$ which is greater than 0.05 . However, there is a significant difference in the librarian's awareness level in CCT adoption among Federal, Private and State university libraries at a $.000$ significant level. This is justified by the mean difference values according to the libraries.

Table 4.1.9. 2: Post-Hoc Hochberg's GT2 Homogeneous subsets

Libraries according to type	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Federal University Library	202	2.7309	
State University Library	53	2.8165	
Private University Library	18		3.8535
Sig.		0.903	1.000

The non-significant difference in Librarians’ levels of awareness of CCT adoption between Federal and State libraries is further justified by a mean difference of 2.73 and 2.82 at $P = 0.903 > 0.05$, the significant level. The level of awareness by librarians from the Private University Library is significantly different from the other libraries, with a mean difference of 3.8535 at $p = 1.000 > 0.05$ significant level. This indicates a significant difference in Librarians’ awareness of CCT adoption across Federal, State, and Private University libraries in NE, Nigeria. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected while the alternative

hypothesis is adopted in the study. This was further justified in the mean
 Figure 4. 1: Mean Plot of Librarian’s level of Awareness

Findings

Based on the analyses and data presented, the following is a summary of findings:

The librarians’ level of awareness of CCT in university libraries in North-East Nigeria was determined to be average, with a mean score of 2.82 on a scale of 5.

In comparing the difference between librarians’ level of awareness of CCT adoption among Federal, State and Private University libraries in North-East Nigeria, the result indicated no significant difference between Federal and State university libraries, and there existed a significant difference between Federal, State and Private university libraries using the post hoc Hochberg’s GT2 test.

Discussion

The result of the research question on the level of awareness of the following CCT in Libraries revealed that the awareness is above average, with a mean score of 2.82. on the scale of points. The results show that most of the librarians were aware of the technologies emanating from the questions asked in the

questionnaire, with the highest mean score of 3.99 for social networking tools such as Facebook, YouTube, Twitter and WhatsApp. This holds true as most of the respondents may be using these applications for personal use most of the time. The awareness of the Discovery tools such as ExLibris Primo, Summon, OCLC WorldCat Discovery Services, BiblioCore, Axiell Arena and ELiDOC iguana scored the least, with a mean score of 2.27. The awareness at above average corroborates the findings of Zubairu 2021 on the awareness and adoption of cloud computing in Nigerian Libraries which reveals that awareness of CCT is good at an average of 92.5% among 44 respondents from Adeleke University Ede, Bowen University, Iwo, Joseph Ayo Babalola, Ekije-Arakije and Redeemers University Ede, all were Private universities in Osun State, South-west Nigeria. The finding is also in agreement with the results obtained by Njoku and Ken-Agbiriogu (2021) in a study to determine the awareness and use of cloud in academic libraries in Imo State, Nigeria, with a mean score of 3.5, indicating high awareness. However, the finding contradicts the study by Pillai and Seena (2018) on the application and awareness of CCT at Kerala University, which found that 42.16% of library staff have little knowledge of cloud computing. Similarly, the result contradicts the findings of Aiyebilehin et al. (2020), who examined the awareness of CCT among librarians in the Ambrose Alli University, Benson Idahosa University, and University of Benin libraries. The results indicated a high level of awareness of cloud computing services such as OCLC and Google Docs, with means of 3.16 and 3.23, respectively.

The results of H_{02} revealed that there is no significant difference between Librarians' level of awareness of CCT adoption among Federal, State and Private University Libraries in North-East, Nigeria. It is revealed that there is no significant difference in librarians' awareness level of CCT and adoption between Federal and State University Libraries, with $p = .798$, which is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. However, there is a significant difference in the librarian's awareness level in CCT adoption between Federal University Libraries and Private University Libraries, as $p=.000$, which is less than $\alpha=0.05$. Similarly, there is a significant difference in librarians' awareness of CCT and adoption between Private and State university libraries at the .000 significant level. This is justified by the mean difference values according to the libraries with Federal and State University libraries at 2.73 and 2.82, with $p=0.903$, which is greater than the α value of 0.05 obtained from the Post-Hoc Hochberg's GT2 Homogeneous subsets. The mean of Federal University libraries (2.73) and that of State University libraries (2.83) appeared in the same subset, indicating there was no significant difference between the Federal and State University libraries, while the mean of Private University libraries (3.8535) appeared in different subset, indicating a significant difference between Private University libraries and that of Federal and State university libraries. This finding is justified by the result of a study conducted by Oriogu et al. (2018), on faculty awareness, perception, and use of information resources and services at a Private university in Nigeria. The results indicated that the level of awareness among the academic staff of Afe Babalola University which is a Private university in Nigeria is high. Similarly, Acheampong et al. (2019) in their study on the awareness of electronic journals found that the awareness is low, with only 43% showing a significant level of awareness among students in Kumasi Technical University, Kumasi, Ghana, which is a government-owned university.

Conclusion

This study assessed the level of awareness of cloud computing technologies among librarians in university libraries in North-East Nigeria and examined variations across Federal, State, and Private institutions. The findings indicate that librarians' overall awareness of cloud computing technologies is moderate, suggesting a reasonable level of familiarity with commonly used platforms such as social networking tools

and online databases. However, awareness remains relatively low for specialised cloud-based applications, including institutional repositories, discovery tools, and online data collection services.

The comparative analysis revealed no statistically significant difference in awareness levels between Federal and State university libraries. In contrast, Private university libraries demonstrated significantly higher awareness levels, reflecting stronger institutional investment in ICT infrastructure, training opportunities, and innovation-driven practices. These disparities highlight the uneven distribution of technological exposure and capacity across institutional categories in the region.

The study underscores the importance of sustained capacity building, targeted sensitisation programmes, and strategic ICT planning to strengthen librarians' awareness and preparedness for cloud-based service delivery. Enhancing librarians' competencies in emerging cloud technologies will improve the efficiency, accessibility, and scalability of academic library services, thereby supporting teaching, learning, and research in Nigerian higher education institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The University libraries in the North-East Nigeria should come up with a sustainability plan such as collaborations, donations, IT resources sharing through consortiums, source for interventions from governmental and non-governmental agencies, in order to increase the availability of electronic information resources and services which is key to adoption of CCT with a view to increase efficiency of library services and the level of users' satisfaction.
2. The university libraries in the North-East Zone, Nigeria should come up with a sustainability plan to increase the awareness of librarians through symposiums, workshops and trainings to enhance on the current level of awareness of librarians of the existing e-resources and communicate managements' decision on anticipated deployment of new innovations to the right personnel at the right time.
3. Libraries should make it as a policy to periodically train the librarians to keep them abreast with the new trends in information and communication technologies as new technologies evolve frequently. Capacity building through workshops or trainings should be organised as the need may arise when a new innovation emerges. This will make librarians to be well motivated to quick embrace new advances.
4. University libraries in the North-East Nigeria should give emphasis to the need to utilize ICT devices in the day-to-day library tasks and furthermore furnish the library and the librarians with the vital ICT facilities and skills needed to support the utilization of ICT devices for library services particularly in the area of e-library which can act as a springboard towards migration of library service to the cloud environment.
5. Federal and State university libraries need to do more like Private universities in terms of acquisitions of innovative information resources and capacity building.

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